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Guru Nanak's Bani in the Context of Gender and Spirituality

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Abstract

Traditionally, theological perspectives have inclined to depicting an image of women-portraying them as "pure and untouched" by maintaining that a pious woman must preserve her sexual chastity. Women were regarded as the chief obstacle to salvation and destroying the souls of men. Guru Nanak, the prophet of humankind empowered the condition of woman and uttered his revealed knowledge in feminine form. Guru Nanak taught that a woman bears the suffering caused by the pains of labour, but she forgets them in the joy of creation. She is essentially not the object of men's lust, but is the mother, the maker, the leader. The menstruation cycle is the mode of creation, but the squalor intention of men considered it as filthy process. But Guru Nanak believed that

"As a woman has her periods, month after month, So does falsehood dwell in the mouth of the false; they suffer forever, again and again. They are not called pure, who sit down after merely washing their bodies. Only they are pure, O Nanak, within whose minds the Lord abides".

Keywords Women, discrimination, Nanak, Lords.

Introduction

Guru Nanak taught that this is the tendency of the society to commodify women as an object of amusement or as pleasure. With the passage of time, owing to socio-political turmoil and the gradual blurring of right ideology, resulting in degeneration of values, women began to lose their due place and were relegated to a lower position. This deplorable subordination begins with theological aspects of creation of mankind that God created man stronger than woman. Guru Nanak said that women sacrificed their whole life to please the men, but men consider this fidelity infidel.

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to study the Guru Nanak's Bani in the context of gender and spirituality.

Review of Literature

For this paper many studies has been done i.e. Jakobsh, Doris R.(2010), Sikhism and Women: History, Texts, and Experience, Kaura, Bhupinder.(2000), Status of Women in Sikhism, Hooks, Bell (2000), Feminism Is for Everybody: Passionate Politics, Gilla, Mahindara Kaura (1995), The role and Status of Women in Sikhism etc have been reviewed for this paper.

Main Text

Woman is the mother, the maker, the leader of the society. Through whom the society begins to grow, through whom the soul gets its body, through whom we learn how to speak and move. But the society of the 15th-16th century considered woman as nothing, but as the source of pleasure as well as machine to produce child. Some consider woman

as slave, while others consider them as sex toys. Even the people practicing the religious rituals considered woman as an obstacle to the salvation of man.

Human mentality is only to commodify all the living beings for their use. Women is different from men only through the physical body, not the through her spirit. All living beings consider the same spirit of the Almighty One. As it is mentioned

Dhharan Gagan Neh Dhaekho Dhoe ||

In the earth and in the sky, I do not see any second.

Naaree Purakh Sabaeee Loe ||3||

Among all the women and the men, His Light is shining. ||3||

Rav Sas Dhaekho Dheepak Oujiaalaa ||

In the lamps of the sun and the moon, I see His Light.

Sarab Niranthar Preetham Baalaa ||4||

Dwelling among all is my ever-youthful Beloved. ||4||

Kar Kirapaa Maeraa Chith Laaeiaa ||

In His Mercy, He attuned my consciousness to the Lord.” (Guru Granth Sahib, p.223)

God is the Supreme Energy, which can neither be created nor be destroyed and it is Formless. God is beyond our intelligence, our senses, our physical power. God is the omnipresent, omniscient, and the Primal being Guru Nanak used the term “*Ik Onkar*” to tell that God is the most knowledgeable, most powerful being and we are just like the puppets of this Primal Truth and He cannot be a male or female like human beings. God has a divine body, which is far and far superior than our body. That is why, Gurbani mentions (Guru Arjan, pg 1144)

*Thou O Lord, art my father and Thou my mother.
Thou art the Giver of peace
to my soul and very life.*

God has qualities of both Father and Mother. God punish us like Father and cared us like a mother. It is said by the one of the Nanak jyot “*Just as the mother, having given birth to a son, feeds him and keeps him in her vision – indoors and outdoors, she puts food in his mouth; each and every moment, she caresses him. In just the same way, the True Guru protects His GurSikhs, who love their Beloved Lord. ||1||*” (Guru Granth Sahib, p.168)

This materialistic world and this physical body is given by the True Lord only to surrender unto Him and to serve Him. But the man believed that woman is impure and also treat her as a potent instrument of destroying the soul of man and also as an obstacle in their path of salvation. Although many contemporary sects worshipped female goddesses with other demi gods to attain the salvation, but they always thought that women are weaker than them.

While women of all classes and religions were suffering from woman, but Guru Nanak empowered them in his bani. Guru Nanak treated himself in the feminine form to express their feelings to the True Lord. He said that God is the Supreme personality of Godhead and the only Husband. The Almighty One, the Akaal Purakh is our husband and we all are His wives. Our motive of this birth is only to enjoin our All- powerful Husband Lord. As Guru Nanak said: Ang 17

aavhu bhainay gal milah ank sahayrhee-aah.
Come, my dear sisters and spiritual companions; hug me close in your embrace.

mil kai karah kahaanee-aa samrath kant kee-aah.
Let's join together, and tell stories of our All-powerful Husband Lord.

saachay saahib sabh gun a-ugan sabh asaah. ||1||

All Virtues are in our True Lord and Master; we are utterly without virtue. ||1||

In Indian tradition, woman is regarded as 'Ardhangini' which means half part of man. Woman is also considered as *Shakti (power)* of God. Keeping asides all the facts that compares a woman to a man, It is the Man's interpretation that he was born to protect woman and to rule on woman and woman's sole purpose was to serve and please man. Due to the societal tendencies, the women are made to believe since time immemorial that they are subordinate to man and are made to support him no matter what. Man forgets that women are placed at the same pedestal as God. As Guru Nanak said in 'Asa di Vaar' –

bhand jammee-ai bhand nimmee-ai bhand mangan vee-aahu.

From woman, man is born; within woman, man is conceived; to woman he is engaged and married.

bhandahu hovai dostee bhandahu chalai raahu.

Woman becomes his friend; through woman, the future generations come.

bhand mu-aa bhand bhaalee-ai bhand hovai banDhaan.

When his woman dies, he seeks another woman; to woman he is bound.

so ki-o mandaa aakhee-ai jit jameh raajaan.

So why call her bad? From her, kings are born.

bhandahu hee bhand oopjai bhandai baajh na ko-ay.

From woman, woman is born; without woman, there would be no one at all.

naanak bhandai baahraa ayko sachaa so-ay.

O Nanak, only the True Lord is without a woman.

jit mukh sadaa salaah-ee-ai bhaagaa ratee chaar.

That mouth which praises the Lord continually is blessed and beautiful.

naanak tay mukh oojlay tit sachai darbaar. ||2||

O Nanak, those faces shall be radiant in the Court of the True Lord. ||2||

Although Guru Nanak in his bani declared that woman is only subordinate to the True Lord but the people did not allowed them to enter in the temples as well as other religious places, especially in the times of their periods. Guru Nanak believed that pure and impure are our deeds not our physical body. Only those people will be punished in the court of the Almighty whose deeds are impure, no one will be punished on the basis of his physical body and his appearance. Guru Nanak was that revolutionary prophet, who challenged that we can not call a woman impure in the months of periods. He said:

mehlaa 1.

First Mehl:

ji-o joroo sirnaavane aavai vaaro vaar.

As a woman has her periods, month after month,

joothay joothaa mukh vasai nit nit ho-ay khu-aar.

so does falsehood dwell in the mouth of the false; they suffer forever, again and again.

soochay ayhi na aakhee-ahi bahan je pindaa Dho-ay.

They are not called pure, who sit down after merely washing their bodies.

soochay say-ee naankaa jin man vasi-aa so-ay. ||2||

Only they are pure, O Nanak, within whose minds the Lord abides. ||2||

Guru Nanak believed that we all are impure and pure in accordance with our mind. If we consider the purity on the basis of physical body, then everyone is impure in this world. Because we all are born from flesh and also conceived within flesh for nine months. Even after birth we are attached with flesh of our mother, then in youth with our wife. Our mouth, tongue, breath, everything is flesh. Guru Nanak believed that we are like the

vessels of the flesh, then how we can consider that we are pure or impure on the basis of our physical body. Even the people who believed that Shudras and women, both are impure and subordinate to the all classes and castes were fools. Guru Nanak taught this philosophy as mentioned as following:

salok mehlaa 1.
Shalok, First Mehl:

pahilaa^N maasahu nimmi-aa maasai andar vaas.
First, the mortal is conceived in the flesh, and then he dwells in the flesh.

jee-o paa-ay maas muhi mili-aa had chamm tan maas.
When he comes alive, his mouth takes flesh; his bones, skin and body are flesh.

maasahu baahar kadhi-aa mammaa maas giraas.
He comes out of the womb of flesh, and takes a mouthful of flesh at the breast.

muhi maasai kaa jeebh maasai kee maasai andar saas.
His mouth is flesh, his tongue is flesh; his breath is in the flesh.

vadaa ho-aa vee-aahi-aa ghar lai aa-i-aa maas.
He grows up and is married, and brings his wife of flesh into his home.

maasahu hee maas oopjai maasahu sabho saak.
Flesh is produced from flesh; all relatives are made of flesh.

satgur mili-ai hukam bujhee-ai taa^N ko aavai raas.
When the mortal meets the True Guru, and realizes the Hukam of the Lord's Command, then he comes to be reformed.

aap chhutay nah chhootee-ai naanak bachan binaas. ||1||
Releasing himself, the mortal does not find release; O Nanak, through empty words, one is ruined. ||1||

Women sacrificed their whole life to please the men, but men consider this fidelity infidel. If women adorn the men that does not mean she is slave. Our modern understanding of this treatment is actually focuses upon discrimination in the religious scriptures. But that's the differences not discrimination. There was the exploitation with the woman in the past but that cannot be considered with the differences ideology of the scriptures. That's why all the Nanak jyots worked against these false rituals like veiling or sacrificing in fire whom we called Hijab and sati system.

If we think that woman through sacrificing her life in the fire shows the true love than we are fools. Because everyone came in our life only to cover some stages of the salvation or for helping us to achieve the love of the Supreme Lover. The main aim of our life is to attain the Supreme Personality of Godhead not to engage fully in the materialism. Guru Nanak believed that materialistic life is also important for the spiritual life. He said that living within this illusionary world, we should renounce the world and can attain the supreme knowledge.

Conclusion

Guru Nanak was the Prophet, who implemented all the universal laws which describes woman as equal to man. Woman was considered unlucky for the society and also as an obstacle to the salvation of man. Woman is created by The True Lord as comparable to man to help him. As believed in the semetic tradition, Woman is the best creation of ther Su[preme personality of Godhead.

Nowadays, women are trying to act in masculine way, due to which they are loosing their real identity. Laws by Prophets and Messengers were made according to the comforts of both the gender, their motive was not to treat woman as inferior. Some laws were misunderstood, through which men are trying to control the woman. Sometimes these misunderstandings also lead to weaken the faith of people on religion as well as The True Lord. Until these teachings and laws are not correctly understood, women will be continuously exploited by men in the veil of Religion...

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